

PYRONES AND RELATED COMPOUNDS. PART VI. BROMINATION OF DIETHYL AND DI-*n*-PROPYL PYRONES

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The bromination of diethyl and dipropyl pyrones unlike pyrone and dimethyl pyrone gives only the dibromopyrones and the prolonged action of bromine results in the fission of the pyrone ring to give tetrabromodiacetyldiethylene ketones. The mechanism of the reaction is given.

Feist and Baum (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 3562) have shown that pyrone (I, R=H) and dimethyl pyrone (I, R=CH₃) in their behaviour towards bromine occupy an intermediate position between benzene and pyridine. For, whereas benzene is easily brominated and pyridine is brominated with great difficulty directly by bromine, the pyrones are brominated with moderate ease giving rise to substitution products which brings them in line with benzene or pyridine, whose bromination results in substitution products only.

The bromination of diethyl and dipropyl pyrones (I, R=C₂H₅ or C₃H₇) synthesised by Deshapande (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 304) was expected to give results similar to pyrone and dimethyl pyrone. In the latter the bromine enters the β -position with respect to the ring oxygen and forms 3 : 5-dibromodimethyl pyrone.

Bromination of diethyl pyrone with an excess of bromine gives a solid perbromide of the brominated pyrone which loses bromine on steam distillation and gives 3 : 5-dibromo-diethylpyrone (III, R=C₂H₅), m.p. 78°. Dipropyl pyrone on similar treatment gives the corresponding bromopyrone (III, R=C₃H₇) which is a liquid. These bromopyrones do not give the reactions of a ketone and thus resemble the unbrominated pyrones (*cf.* Bedekar, Kaushal and Deshapande, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 466). Moreover, they seem to have lost all basic properties as they do not form hydrochloride or chloroplatinate. The bromine atom in them is remarkably stable and so also the oxygen of the ring; for on boiling with strong baryta solution neither the bromine could be replaced by hydroxyl nor the ring could be opened at the oxygen. Sodamide also gives negative results.

Unlike dimethyl pyrone, diethyl and dipropyl pyrones do not give monobromo products like (II). The reaction proceeds even beyond dibromination and the prolonged action on a water-bath brings about the fission of the pyrone ring producing tetrabromo-diethyl or dipropyl diethylene ketones (V, R=C₂H₅ or C₃H₇) from the respective pyrones. The pyrone ring undergoes fission by the hydrobromic acid evolved in the reaction to

form the intermediate product (IV) the tertiary hydroxyl group of which immediately reacts with hydrobromic acid to give the olefinic ketone (V) (cf. Kamm and Marvel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 299).

This is not surprising in view of the fact that tetrahydro pyrones are easily split up to diolefinic ketones by mineral acids (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2801; 1898, 31, 1508; 1899, 32, 809). Thus 2 : 6-diphenyltetrahydropyrone gives dibenzalacetone obviously according to the following change :—

The olefinic ketones (V) are remarkably stable and the peculiarity about them is that they do not react with semicarbazide, phenyl or nitrophenylhydrazine. The inactivity of the carbonyl group is probably due to the steric hindrance offered by the two bromine atoms linked to the adjacent carbon atoms to the carbonyl. They decolourise 1% acid potassium permanganate solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

3 : 5-Dibromodiethyl Pyrone (III, R=C₂H₅).—Diethyl pyrone (4.7 g.) was gradually added in sunlight in about one quarter of an hour to bromine (30 g.), dried over sulphuric acid, containing iodine (0.2 g.) in a flask fitted with a long air condenser and a calcium chloride tube. A vigorous reaction took place in the beginning with evolution of hydrobromic acid, the reaction being completed by heating on a water-bath for 2 hours. On removing the excess of bromine a red crystalline mass separated, which was the perbromide of the brominated pyrone. This was subjected to steam distillation until no more of bromine passed over and the residual oily layer solidified; yield of the crude product, 6.0 g. (60% of theory). It crystallised from 50% alcohol as long fine colourless needles, m.p. 78°. (Found : C, 34.2; H, 3.1; Br, 51.1. C₉H₁₀O₂Br₂ requires C, 34.8; H, 3.2; Br, 51.6 per cent).

3 : 5-Dibromodipropyl Pyrone (III, R=C₃H₇).—Dipropyl pyrone (4 g.) was added gradually to dry bromine (14 g.) containing a little iodine as before and heated on a water-bath for nearly 4 hours to complete the reaction and after removal of excess of bromine the perbromide was subjected to steam distillation when the bromopyrone came out as a red coloured oil. It did not solidify even in ice and was therefore extracted with ether, dried and on removal of ether the bromopyrone was obtained as a red viscous oil, yield 5 g. On distillation under reduced pressure it decomposed at 140°. (Found : Br, 39.2 in the distilled liquid and Br, 46.8 in the crude product. C₁₁H₁₄O₂Br₂ requires Br, 47.3 per cent).

Tetrabromodiethyl-diethylene Ketone (V, R=C₂H₅).—Diethyl pyrone (5 g.) was added in sunlight to bromine (32 g.) dried over sulphuric acid containing a little iodine as before

and the reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for nearly 6 hours. After going through all the stages as in the preparation of dibromodiethyl pyrone, a mixture of the ketone and the bromopyrone was obtained after steam distillation, yield 10 g. (66% of theory). On shaking the mixture with absolute alcohol, the ketone remained undissolved as a white granular crystalline solid, purified by washing it melted at 165°. (Found : C, 23.4 ; H, 1.8 ; Br, 70.3. $C_8H_{10}OBr_4$ requires C, 23.8 ; H, 2.2 ; Br, 70.5 per cent).

From the crude product, dissolved in absolute alcohol, the dibromodiethyl pyrone was isolated by repeated crystallisation from 50% alcohol. Though the mixture contained about 70% of the bromo ketone, only 30% of the ketone and 10% of the bromopyrone could be isolated in the pure condition.

Tetrabromodipropyl-diethylene Ketone (V, R= C_3H_7).—Dipropyl pyrone (2.5 g.) was added to bromine (12 g.) containing a little iodine as in the previous experiments and the mixture heated on a water-bath for 10 hours. The excess of bromine was evaporated and the residue on steam distillation gave an oil which solidified in about three to four days. Purified by repeated washings with absolute alcohol it melted at 160°, yield 3.5 g. (Found : C, 28.0 ; H, 2.8 ; Br, 66.5. $C_{11}H_{14}OBr_4$ requires C, 27.4 ; H, 2.9 ; Br, 66.3 per cent).

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